

Appendix 2 The phylogeny tree of 204 bird species examined for the responses to droughts at individual or population level.

The calculation of phylogenetic distance of species included in the analysis was based on the phylogenetic tree, which was built with the highest overall clade support from a sample of 1,000 phylogenetic trees from the global phylogeny of birds (Jetz et al. 2012) using the maximum-clade-credibility method.

